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JIS

Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

Vision

“ENRICHING BEAUTIFUL MINDS TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS”

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) aims to disseminate scholarly research articles and papers to the wider community with the aim of offering an academic and scientific platform that provides an outlet to authors. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) is an open access online journal. Initially, the JIS will provide an online version, but is planning a print version later in this academic journey. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) focuses on a high-quality academic research articles and papers. All categories of research are of interest to the JIS, including insightful empirical studies, conceptual papers, commentary, essays, and theoretical articles.

JIS is an interdisciplinary platform and invites authors, academics, students, researchers, leaders, managers, scientists for their contributions in the disciplines of sciences, sociology, education, philosophy, humanities and management. Articles and Papers of scientific and academic rigour in Qualitative, Quantitative, Mixed or Blend methods are welcome.

JIS intends to publish two issues per annum (May and November).

Submissions to, and Publication in, the JIS is free.

All papers submitted for publication will be peer reviewed.

Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

mission is to “Guide Beautiful Minds towards Intellectual Enrichment”

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Editorial

Dear Readers,

It is our immense pleasure to announce that the Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) is now indexed in the DOAJ: Directory of Open Access Journals. JIS is also indexed in JUFO: Julkaisufoorumi and NSD- Norwegian Register for Scientific Journals, Series and Publishers. As we commit ourselves to serving the academic and scientific communities, the purpose of serving has deepened even more for “Enriching Beautiful Minds towards Intelligent Minds” in a greater meaning. As we have struggled to reach this far since 2017, we are now even determined to walk extra miles. This encouragement comes from the authors and reviewers who have trusted in our confidence, intelligence, and fairness.

In this volume 9, issue 1 of May 2025, we have published scientific papers from various disciplines and different countries. These published papers are openly accessible to all readers and uploaded to DOAJ and other indexing platforms.

Submission to JIS is welcome from authors from all subjects. We look forward to more participation to Enrich the Beautiful Minds towards Intelligent Minds.

Thank you very much

Let us join and collaborate together to **ENRICH the BEAUTIFUL MINDS
TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS**

Mani Man Singh Rajbhandari. Ph.D.
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